

LINEAR REGRESSION MODEL FOR VARIOUS PRIMES

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ABSTRACT

Despite having a straightforward definition, the prime numbers are filled with mathematical riddles. How prime numbers are dispersed among integers is one such unsolved puzzle. The distribution of primes appears erratic at first glance, but several trends are clear. The asymptotic distribution of prime numbers among positive integers is described by the prime number theorem (PNT) in mathematics. It precisely quantifies the pace at which primes become less common as they grow larger, formalizing the intuitive notion that this happens. The relationship between prime numbers and their hypotheses was the focus of numerous studies. The definition of multidimensional reverse primes and the identification of a linear regression model for diverse primes are presented in this research work. Additionally, a JAVA program for finding the linear regression model has been developed.

Keywords: Multi-dimensional reverse prime; Regression; Primes;

INTRODUCTION

The fact that primes can be thought of as the fundamental units that make up the natural numbers is one of the reasons why they are significant in number theory. Every integer may be factored into a single list of prime numbers, according to the fundamental theorem of mathematics. Therefore, learning about numbers is essentially learning about the characteristics of prime numbers. Over the centuries, mathematicians have learned a lot about prime numbers. There are infinitely many primes, as demonstrated by one of Euclid's most well-known arguments. The Prime Number Theorem was established by mathematicians in the nineteenth century. Theorem provides a rough estimate of how many numbers less than the provided number are prime given some huge natural number. There is a general formula that describes how primes become scarcer as numbers get larger. Despite what we already know about prime numbers, there are still a tonne of seemingly straightforward hypotheses concerning primes that haven't been either confirmed or refuted. Finding a conjecture for prime numbers that may aid in figuring out their distribution as well as be utilized to discover relationships between them is always necessary.

The esoteric relationship between various primes and their analysis in various intervals, as well as the correlation between them, was uncovered by Sharma, D.K., Agarwal, & Uniyal (2022). Super primes, perfect super primes, and non-super primes were defined by Sharma, D. K., and Uniyal, A. S. (2021), along with the frequency of each in a particular time period. According to Sharma, D.K., Agarwal, and Uniyal A.S. (2021), two prime numbers $P_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma} = pqr$ and $P_{\gamma,\beta,\alpha} = rqp$ such that $P_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma} \neq P_{\gamma,\beta,\alpha}$ are known as multi-reverse

primes. Here, p , q , and r are three different prime numbers with α , β , and γ digits respectively. The Fibonacci prime distribution was discovered by Agarwal, S., and Singh (2021), who also created a Java programme to locate Fibonacci primes inside a specified range. Fibonacci primes were also suggested as a way to encrypt and decode data. The suggested solution provides a high level of security against unauthorised access when compared to existing encryption techniques.

Agarwal, S., and Uniyal, A.S. (2015) created a special role for primes because the fundamental theorem states that any number may be factorised as the product of primes. In the study, composite numbers that could be factored by non-repeating primes in pairs were examined. The topic of cryptography key systems has seen the development of specific distributions and their applications. The Fermat and Mersenne prime numbers were also discovered by Debnath L. & Basu K. (2015), who also discussed the distribution of prime numbers, prime number theorems, and the relationship between Euler's and Riemann's zeta functions and prime numbers.

This research identified a brand-new class of primes in this work termed multidimensional reverse primes, and also discovered a linear model for regression between the various prime to ascertain their relationship. Additionally, a JAVA software has been developed to locate the regression line.

MULTI DIMENSIONAL REVERSE PRIME

Let p , q and r be three different primes having α , β and γ digits respectively. If the three numbers $p_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} = pqr$, $p_{\beta, \alpha, \gamma} = qpr$ and $p_{\alpha, \gamma, \beta} = prq$ are primes such that $p_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} \neq p_{\beta, \alpha, \gamma} \neq p_{\alpha, \gamma, \beta}$, β then $p_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma}$, $p_{\beta, \alpha, \gamma}$ and $p_{\alpha, \gamma, \beta}$ are called Multi dimensional reverse primes.

Example: $p_{1,2,2} = 71713$, $p_{2,1,2} = 17713$ and $p_{1,2,2} = 71317$ are multi dimensional reverse primes as 7, 17 and 13 are three different primes such that $71713 \neq 17713 \neq 71317$.

Corollary-1: Below 100000 all Mersenne primes are super primes.

All Mersenne primes below 100000 are 3, 7, 31, 127, 8191 and these all numbers are also super primes.

Corollary-2: 3 is only prime number which is also Mersenne, Fibonacci, Fermat, Lucas as well as Super primes.

ANALYSIS OF SUPER PRIMES AND DIGITAL SUPER PRIMES IN DIFFERENT INTERVALS

The examination of super primes and digital super primes was presented by Sharma, D.K., Agarwal, S. & Uniyal, A.S. (2022) in the various intervals depicted in Table-1.

Table-1

	1	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	900
	to	00								
	10	0	00							
		to								

	00 0	20 00 0	30 00 0	40 00 0	50 00 0	60 00 0	70 00 0	80 00 0	90 00 0	100 000
No. of Su per pri me s	55 1	36 8	44 9	33 4	33 1	37 6	34 4	25 2	36 0	288
No. of Dig ital Su per pri me s	24 3	16 1	19 6	14 2	13 0	15 1	98	92	14 6	103

EQUATION TO THE LINE OF REGRESSION BETWEEN SUPER PRIMES AND DIGITAL SUPER PRIMES

Number of Super primes (X)	Number of Digital Super prime (Y)	$d_x = X - A$ where $A = 331$	$d_y = Y - B$ where $B = 130$	d_x^2	d_y^2	$d_x d_y$
551	243	220	113	48400	12769	24860
368	161	37	31	1369	961	1147
449	196	118	66	13924	4356	7788
334	142	3	12	9	144	36
331	130	0	0	0	0	0
376	151	45	21	2025	441	945
344	98	13	-32	169	1024	-416
252	92	-79	-38	6241	1444	3002
360	146	29	16	841	256	464
288	103	-43	-27	1849	729	1161
		$\sum d_x =$ 343	$\sum d_y =$ 162	$\sum d_x^2$ =74827	$\sum d_y^2$ =22124	$\sum d_x d_y$ =38987

Here $n = 10$

Now: Regression coefficient of X on Y

$$b_{xy} = \frac{n \sum dx dy - \sum dx \sum dy}{n \sum dy^2 - (\sum dy)^2}$$

$$b_{xy} = \frac{10 \times 38987 - 343 \times 162}{221240 - 26244} = \frac{389870 - 55566}{194996} = \frac{334304}{194996} = 1.7 \text{ (approx)}$$

and Regression coefficient of Y on X

$$b_{yx} = \frac{n \sum dx dy - \sum dx \sum dy}{n \sum dx^2 - (\sum dx)^2}$$

$$b_{yx} = \frac{10 \times 38987 - 343 \times 162}{748270 - 117649} = \frac{389870 - 55566}{630621} = 0.5 \text{ (approx)}$$

Now the equation of regression line of X on Y is

$$X - A = b_{xy} (Y - B)$$

$$X - 331 = 1.7 (Y - 130)$$

$$\boxed{X = 1.7 Y + 110}$$

And the equation of regression line of Y on X

$$Y - B = b_{yx} (X - A)$$

$$Y - 130 = 0.5 (X - 331)$$

$$\boxed{Y = 0.5 X - 35.5}$$

ANALYSIS OF TWIN PRIMES AND SUPER TWIN PRIMES IN DIFFERENT INTERVALS

The examination of twin primes and super twin primes in different intervals is shown in Table-2 by Sharma, D.K., Agarwal, S. & Uniyal, A.S. (2022).

Table-2

	1 to 10 00 00	10 to 20 00 00	20 to 30 00 00	30 to 40 00 00	40 to 50 00 00	50 to 60 00 00	60 to 70 00 00	70 to 80 00 00	80 to 90 00 00	900 000 to 100 000 0
No · of T wi n pri me s	12 24	93 6	83 4	81 0	76 1	76 6	73 0	70 5	70 6	697

No · of Su pe r T wi n pri me s	19 4	11 8	14 0	71	88	10 4	67	52	91	78
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EQUATION TO THE LINE OF REGRESSION BETWEEN TWIN PRIMES AND SUPER TWIN PRIMES

Num ber of Twin prime s (X)	No. of Sup er twin pri me (Y)	d_x = X-A where A = 761	d_y = Y-B where B = 88	d_x²	d_y²	d_xd_y
1224	194	463	106	214369	11236	49078
936	118	175	30	30625	900	5250
834	140	73	52	5329	2704	3796
810	71	49	-17	2401	289	-833
761	88	0	0	0	0	0
766	104	5	16	25	256	80
730	67	-31	-21	961	441	651
705	52	-56	-36	3136	1296	2016
706	91	-55	3	3025	9	-165
697	78	-64	-10	4096	100	640
		∑d_x²=5 59	∑d_y=1 23	∑d_x²=263 967	∑d_y²=17 231	∑d_xd_y=60 513

Here n = 10

Now: Regression coefficient of X on Y

$$b_{xy} = \frac{n \sum d_x d_y - \sum d_x \sum d_y}{n \sum d_y^2 - (\sum d_y)^2}$$

$$b_{xy} = \frac{605130 - 68757}{172310 - 15129} = \frac{536373}{157181} = 3.4 \text{ (approx)}$$

and Regression coefficient of Y on X

$$b_{yx} = \frac{n \sum dx dy - \sum dx \sum dy}{n \sum dx^2 - (\sum dx)^2}$$
$$b_{yx} = \frac{605130 - 68757}{2639670 - 312481} = \frac{536373}{2327189} = 0.2 \text{ (approx)}$$

Now the equation of regression line of X on Y is

$$X - A = b_{xy} (Y - B)$$

$$X - 761 = 3.4 (Y - 88)$$

$$\boxed{X = 3.4 Y + 461.5}$$

And the equation of regression line of Y on X

$$Y - B = b_{yx} (X - A)$$

$$Y - 88 = 0.2 (X - 761)$$

$$\boxed{Y = 0.2 X - 64.2}$$

JAVA PROGRAM TO FIND THE LINE OF REGRESSION BETWEEN VARIOUS PRIMES

```
import java.util.*;
import java.lang.*;
class Regression
{
public static void main(String args[])
{
Scanner in=new Scanner(System.in);
double x[],y[],dx[],dy[],xx[],yy[],dxdy[];
double A,B,sumx=0,sumy=0,sumxx=0,sumyy=0,sumdxdy=0,bxy,byx;
int i,n;
System.out.print("Enter number of values :");
n=in.nextInt();
x =new double[n];
y =new double[n];
dx =new double[n];
dy =new double[n];
xx =new double[n];
yy =new double[n];
dxdy =new double[n];
System.out.print("Enter values of x :");
for(i=0;i<n;i++)
{
x[i]=in.nextDouble();
}
System.out.print("Enter values of y :");
for(i=0;i<n;i++)
```

```
{
  y[i]=in.nextDouble();
}
System.out.print("Enter assumed mean of series x :");
A=in.nextDouble();
System.out.print("Enter assumed mean of series y :");
B=in.nextDouble();
for(i=0;i<n;i++)
{
  dx[i]=x[i]-A;
  dy[i]=y[i]-B;
  xx[i]=dx[i]*dx[i];
  yy[i]=dy[i]*dy[i];
  dxdy[i]=dx[i]*dy[i];
  sumx=sumx+dx[i];
  sumy=sumy+dy[i];
  sumxx=sumxx+xx[i];
  sumyy=sumyy+yy[i];
  sumdxdy=sumdxdy+dxdy[i];
}
bxy=(n*sumdxdy-sumx*sumy)/(n*sumyy-sumy*sumy);
byx=(n*sumdxdy-sumx*sumy)/(n*sumxx-sumx*sumx);
String s1 = String.format("%.1f",bxy);
bxy = Double.parseDouble(s1);
String s2 = String.format("%.1f",byx);
byx = Double.parseDouble(s2);
System.out.println("Regression Coefficient of x on y :"+bxy);
System.out.println("Regression Coefficient of y on x :"+byx);
System.out.println("\n\nEquation of regression line of x on y is :\n\n"+"X = "+bxy+"Y +
"+(A-bxy*B));
System.out.println("\n\nEquation of regression line of y on x is :\n\n"+"Y = "+byx+"X +
"+(B-byx*A));
```

CONCLUSION

In this study the definition of multi dimensional reverse prime has been given and tried to determine the line of regression between various primes, which is beneficial for finding the relationship among them and to develop a conjecture for the distribution of different primes. A JAVA program has also been developed to find the regression lines between the prime numbers, which will aid in the investigation of the complex relationship between various primes.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sharma, D.K., Agarwal, S., & Uniyal, A.S. (2022). Neoteric Relationship between Various Primes and Their Analysis. *Stochastic Modeling and Applications*, Vol.26(1), 155-162.
- [2] Sharma, D.K., Agarwal, S., & Uniyal, A.S. (2021). Distribution of Multi-Reverse Primes within the Given Interval & Their Application in Asymmetric Cryptographic Algorithm. *International Journal of Applied Engineering & Technology*, Vol.3(1), 29-33.
- [3] Agarwal, A., Agarwal, S. & Singh, B.K. (2021). Analysis of Fibonacci Primes & Their Application in Cryptography. *Stochastic Modeling and Applications*, Vol.25(2), 73-82.
- [4] Agarwal, S., Sharma, D. & Uniyal, A.S. (2021). Formulation & Distribution of Super Primes. *Global and Stochastic Analysis*, Vol.8(2), 155-166.
- [5] Agarwal, S. & Uniyal, A.S. (2015). Multiprimes Distribution within a Given Norms. *International Journal of Applied Mathematical Sciences*, Vol.8(2), 126-132.
- [6] Debnath L. & Basu K. (2015). Some Analytical and Computational Aspects of Prime Numbers, Prime Number Theorems and Distribution of Primes with Applications. *Int. J. Appl. Comput. Math* 1:3–32.